

Protocol: The effect of non-caloric soft drinks on mental disorders in patients with and without diabetes

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Study information

Description

Mental disorders are a major and growing global health challenge, affecting nearly one in seven individuals worldwide (1) and highlighting the need to identify modifiable risk factors. One emerging lifestyle factor is the rising consumption of low- and non-caloric soft drinks (NCS) (2), with over one-third of European adults reporting weekly intake [TE. (3), and the global market is expected to more than double by 2032 (4). The market is particularly replacing sugar-sweetened beverages (SSB) with NCS.

This rapid expansion has coincided with a growing body of observational research linking NCS consumption to higher risks of mental disorders such as depression

(5–11) and anxiety (6,9,11). However, despite these associations, existing studies are limited by small sample sizes (6,8,9), reliance on self-reported outcomes (5,6,8–10), and a predominant focus on depression and anxiety. Two studies have been conducted on UK Biobank data; however, they rely solely on ICD-10 codes. Most cases of depression and anxiety may be managed at the primary care level, and this approach may markedly underestimate common mental disorders and bias case identification toward more severe phenotypes.

Substitution analyses suggest that replacing NCS with SSB, coffee, tea, or milk does not substantially lower the risk of depression or anxiety (11), although replacing them with natural juices appears protective for both depression and anxiety (7,11). Beyond mood and anxiety disorders, only two smaller studies have examined the associations between NCS and eating disorders (ED)

(12,13), but neither examined the prospective risk in healthy populations. To the best of our knowledge, no studies have investigated the effect of NCS D on other mental disorders apart from those mentioned above.

Beyond the impact on the general population, individuals with type 2 diabetes (T2D) may be particularly susceptible to NCS D-related mental health risks due to shared pathophysiological mechanisms, including alterations in the gut microbiome, inflammation, hormonal and neurotransmitter imbalances, and vascular dysfunction. Furthermore, T2D itself is an established risk factor for mental disorders, potentially creating an additive effect. Although current dietary guidelines for individuals with T2D recommend replacing SSB with NCS D (14), previous studies have not examined whether diabetes status moderates the relationship between NCS D intake and mental health outcomes.

This research will use the UK Biobank Resource under Application Number 81520.

Objectives and hypotheses

This study aims to examine the prospective association between NCS D intake and the development of mental disorders, and to test whether this association is moderated by T2D status.

We hypothesize that NCS D intake is associated with a higher long-term risk of mental disorders compared to both SSB intake and to abstention from soft drinks, and that individuals with T2D are particularly vulnerable to the effect of NCS D on the association.

To test these hypotheses, we will use data from the UK Biobank to prospectively assess whether baseline NCS D intake predicts the onset of multiple mental disorders, including substance use, schizophrenia spectrum, mood, neurotic, eating, and personality disorders, in individuals with and without T2D. We will also perform substitution analyses to evaluate the effects of replacing NCS D with SSB, coffee, tea, milk, and natural juices. If associations are found, we will conduct causal mediation analyses to explore potential biological mechanisms. Findings from this study may help inform dietary guidelines for individuals with and without T2D to reduce mental health risks.

Design plan

Study type

Observational Study. Data is collected from study subjects that are not randomly assigned to a treatment. This includes surveys, natural experiments, and regression discontinuity designs.

Blinding

No blinding is involved in this study.

Study design

The study is an observational cohort study using data from the UK Biobank, a prospective cohort comprising more than half a million participants aged 37 to 73 years, collected between 2006 and 2010 (15).

Sampling plan

Existing data

Registration prior to analysis of the data. As of the date of submission, the data exist and you have accessed it, though no analysis has been conducted related to the research plan (including calculation of summary statistics). A common situation for this scenario when a large dataset exists that is used for many different studies over time, or when a data set is randomly split into a sample for exploratory analyses, and the other section of data is reserved for later confirmatory data analysis.

Explanation of existing data

The UK Biobank is a large national cohort of participants in the UK, with data collected in a standardized format the the sole purpose of providing a data resource for researchers to use for health research. All information about collection procedures, limitations, and sources of bias are well established and described by the UK Biobank resource.

Because of its size of data collected, it is near impossible to a priori see patterns in the data that might influence how the analysis will be conducted, unless specifically looked for or previously published on. In this way, we feel pre-analysis bias is minimal.

Data collection procedures

Exposure:

NCS D consumption will be derived from the Oxford WebQ 24-hour dietary recall questionnaire, completed up to five times between 2009 and 2012 (16,17).

Outcome:

We will identify all hospital records of mental disorders from the UK Biobank, categorized according to ICD-10 (see Table 1) and general practitioner (GP) clinical records (Read codes, Clinical Terms Version 3 (CTV3) and Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine – Clinical Terms (SNOMED CT) mapped to ICD-10. GP clinical data is available for 45% of the cohort. For the sensitivity analysis, we will also include information on prescriptions of psychopharmacological agents and self-reported mental disorders.

Covariates:

Data on age, sex, ethnicity, socioeconomic status (measured by the Townsend Deprivation Index), physical activity, smoking status and other dietary information were collected via questionnaires. Body mass index (BMI) was calculated from height and weight measured during the initial visit at an assessment center. For a subgroup of participants in the UK Biobank (17), biomarkers were obtained from blood samples.

Sample size

Sample size rationale

We are using the sample size available in the UK Biobank. A total of 210,965 individuals completed one or more 24-hour dietary assessments (18). The sample size after application of the exclusion criteria is not yet known.

Variables

Measures variables

Exposure:

For participants with multiple 24-hour dietary recalls, we will average NCS intake across available recalls to represent habitual consumption (servings/day).

Outcomes:

The primary outcome is incident mental disorders (all and sub-categorized) evaluated through ICD-10 codes and GP clinical records. For secondary analysis, we will include prescription data and self-reported mental disorders.

Covariates and biomarkers:

We will obtain data on the following covariates: age, sex, ethnicity, socioeconomic status (measured by the Townsend Deprivation Index), physical activity, smoking status, other dietary information and body mass index (BMI). We will include information on all dietary intake, as measured by 24-hour recalls, and group them into larger categories such as vegetables, fruits, dairy, fish, and meat. Diabetes status will be based on multi-source information, including data from primary and secondary care, medication use, and biomarkers (HbA1c). Biomarkers include lipid profiles, amino acids, hormone levels, metabolic, inflammatory, oxidative stress, and neurodegenerative markers.

Analysis plan

Statistical models

Descriptive statistics will include baseline characteristics (age, sex, socioeconomic status, physical activity, BMI) of the overall population and subgroups defined by NCS intake and T2D status.

The main analysis is to examine the associations between NCS intake and psychiatric disorders compared to no soft drink intake (reference) and SSB intake, we will compute cumulative incidences and calculate hazard ratios (HRs) and 95 % confidence intervals (CIs) using Cox proportional hazards models. Age will be used as the time scale. We will follow participants from baseline, the most recent response to a 24-hour dietary recall, until censoring due to death, loss to follow-up, end of study, or the first occurrence of the outcome, whichever occurs first. The primary outcome is all mental disorders.

Model 1 will be a crude, unadjusted model. Model 2 will be adjusted for age, sex, Townsend Deprivation Index, and ethnicity. Model 3 will also be adjusted for physical activity, smoking status, alcohol intake, and other dietary intake (grouped into broader categories such as vegetables, fruits, dairy, fish, and meat). Model 4 will, furthermore, also be adjusted for BMI and diabetes status.

Secondary and sensitivity analysis include six major mental outcome groups: 1. mental and behavioral disorders due to psychoactive substance abuse, 2. schizophrenia and related disorders, 3. mood disorders, 4. neurotic, stress-related and somatoform disorders (including anxi-

ety), 5. eating disorders and 6. personality disorders. Sub-analysis will be stratified by diabetes status.

We will do a Substitution analysis to incorporate specified substitution models (19) to assess the association of replacing NCS with SSB, natural juices, milk, tea, and coffee.

We will conduct the following sensitivity analyses: 1) exclude early events (<2 years follow-up), 2) use baseline diet only, 3) use only participants with more than one 24-hour dietary questionnaire, 4) include pharmacological treatments and self-reported mental disorders in our outcome measurement for the overall estimate of risk of mental disorders, 5) stratify by age (over and under 60 years of age) and 6) restrict the sample to participants with no history of any mental disorder at baseline (ICD-10 codes or GP records) to evaluate whether the associations persisted in participants without any recorded mental disorder before baseline.

Lastly, we will do a mediation analysis if we find an association between NCS intake and mental disorders. We will estimate the interventional direct and indirect effect using state-of-the-art causal mediation analysis methods. Mediators may include lipid profiles, amino acids, hormone levels, metabolic markers, inflammatory markers, oxidative stress markers, and neurodegenerative markers.

Transformations

None that we can foresee at this time.

Inference criteria

Significance level: A p-value less than 0.05 will be regarded as statistically significant. Hazard ratios (HRs) and 95% confidence intervals (CIs) will be provided.

Data exclusion

Participants with prevalent mental disorder of the disorder of interest at baseline (defined by ICD-10 codes or GP records) will be excluded. Similarly, participants with implausible energy intake (<800 or >4200 kcal/day for men; <500 or >3500 kcal/day for women) will also be excluded. Outliers in covariates such as BMI, physical activity, and income will also be evaluated.

Missing data

We will address missing data using multiple imputation methods when suitable. If a covariate has a high proportion of missing data, we will conduct sensitivity analyses to assess the robustness of our findings.

Exploratory analyses (optional)

If sufficient data are available, we will examine the relationship between NCS intake and BMI.

Other

This research will use the UK Biobank Resource under Application Number 81520.

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